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##### R-Script explaining manual forward selection #####

# The manual forward selection has the objective to identify environmental parameters where each
# explains a separate dimension of variance in the taxa data (i.e. that show no collinearity between
# each other). By following this procedure, we will obtain a set of independent forcing variables that
# drive the taxa assemblage.

#####

# Ranking the 6 parameters by eigenvalue (the amount of taxa variance they explain):

rda(TAXA ~ PARAMETER.X, data=ENVI)

# Result: SSTsummer (12.7%), Sealce (9.7%), SSSsummer (6.9%), PPsummer (4.6%), PPannual
# (4.2%), PPspring (2.5%)

# Evaluating the independence between all 6 parameters:
# To this end we calculated Variance Inflation Factors (VIF), expressing how much of the taxa
# variance explained by one environmental variable is already explained by another parameter. The
# VIF of a variable is calculated from the multiple correlations (r) among the environmental variables
# (ter Braak and Smilauer 2002), using the equation  $VIF = 1/(1-r^2)$ . We chose a cut-off value of  $VIF \leq 2$ 
# for all parameters as also suggested in other studies (e.g., Lopes et al. 2010). Such a VIF value only
# allows collinearities of  $r^2 \leq 0.5$  and thus not more than half of the variance in the taxa data explained
# by one variable to also be explained by another variable.

# Now we start with the actual forward selection:
# After ranking the 6 variables by their eigenvalue we start with the first one and add step-by-step
# another variable and check if the VIF's < 2.

n.rda <- rda(TAXA ~ SSTsummer+Sealce, data=ENVI)
vif.cca(n.rda)

# VIF < 2? YES
# Result:      SSTsummer   Sealce
#           1.78         1.78
# Taxa variance explained: 18.7%

# Proceede with the above model and add the next parameter:

n.rda <- rda(TAXA ~ SSTsummer+Sealce+SSSsummer, data=ENVI)
vif.cca(n.rda)

# VIF < 2? NO
# Result:      SSTsummer   Sealce   SSSsummer
#           2.13         2.60     1.46
# We find that two parameters show too much collinearity. To decide which parameters to keep and
# which to exclude from the set of independent forcing variables, we check which model explains more
# taxa variance and how large the VIFs are:

n.rda<-rda(TAXA ~ SSTsummer+Sealce, data=ENVI)
# Taxa variance explained: 18.7%   VIFs: SSTsummer 1.78 Sealce 1.78

n.rda<-rda(TAXA ~ SSSsummer+Sealce, data=ENVI)
# Taxa variance explained: 17.5%   VIFs: SSSsummer 1.23 Sealce 1.23

n.rda<-rda(TAXA ~ SSSsummer+SSTsummer, data=ENVI)
# Taxa variance explained: 19.6% VIFs: SSTsummer 1.00 SSSsummer 1.00

# The model including SSTsummer and SSSsummer (excluding Sealce) is the better model explaining
# the largest amount of taxa variance and showing the highest amount of independence.
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# Note:
# We exclude Sealce from our dataset because it does not explain a separate dimension of variance
# in taxa assemblages within the regional Baffin Bay dataset. This does not mean, that it cannot be
# reconstructed or does not explain taxa variance! However, our analysis suggests that SSTsummer
# and Sealce "play the same part" in driving assemblage compositions, meaning that by
# reconstructing one we actually reconstruct a "mixture" of SSTsummer and Sealce. This is
# strengthened by the result of the MFA where we detected SST on the one end of the first dimension
# and Sealce on the other end. However, to calibrate an independent dataset, we need to decide
# between SSTsummer and Sealce. Statistics favour SSTsummer. But, we have to bear in mind when
# applying the independent calibration dataset that the SSTsummer parameter is a place holder for
# several temperature parameters like SSTsummer, Sealce and presumably others.
```

```
# Proceede with the best performing model and add the next variable
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```
n.rda <- rda(TAXA ~ SSTsummer+SSSummer+Ppsummer, data=ENVI)
vif.cca(n.rda)
```

```
# VIF < 2? NO
```

```
# Result:      SSTsummer   SSSsummer   Ppsummer
#             1.87         1.22         2.08
```

```
# We follow the same procedure as above: Which model explains more variance and how large are
# the VIFs?
```

```
n.rda <- rda(TAXA ~ SSSsummer+Ppsummer, data=ENVI)
# Taxa variance explained: 10.2%   VIFs: SSSsummer 1.11 Ppsummer 1.11
```

```
n.rda <- rda(TAXA ~ SSTsummer+SSSummer, data=ENVI)
# Taxa variance explained: 19.6%   VIFs: SSTsummer 1.00 SSSsummer 1.00
```

```
n.rda <- rda(TAXA ~ SSTsummer+Ppsummer, data=ENVI)
# Taxa variance explained: 17.6%   VIFs: SSTsummer 1.71 Ppsummer 1.71
```

```
# Proceede with the best performing model and add the next variable
```

```
n.rda <- rda(TAXA ~ SSTsummer+SSSummer+Ppannual, data=ENVI)
vif.cca(n.rda)
```

```
# VIF < 2? NO
```

```
# Result:      SSTsummer   SSSsummer   Ppannual
#             2.11         1.09         2.19
```

```
# We follow the same procedure as above: Which model explains more variance and how large are
# the VIFs?
```

```
n.rda <- rda(TAXA ~ SSSsummer+Ppannual, data=ENVI)
# Taxa variance explained: 10.4%   VIFs: SSSsummer 1.04 Ppannual 1.04
```

```
n.rda <- rda(TAXA ~ SSTsummer+SSSummer, data=ENVI)
# Taxa variance explained: 19.6%   VIFs: SSTsummer 1.00 SSSsummer 1.00
```

```
n.rda <- rda(TAXA ~ SSTsummer+Ppannual, data=ENVI)
# Taxa variance explained: 17.7%   VIFs: SSTsummer 2.01 Ppsummer 2.01
```

```
# Proceede with the best performing model and add the next (last) variable
```

```
n.rda <- rda(TAXA ~ SSTsummer+SSSummer+Ppspring, data=ENVI)
vif.cca(n.rda)
```

```
# VIF < 2? YES
```

```
# Result:      SSTsummer   SSSsummer   Ppspring
#             1.81         1.00         1.81
```

```
# Taxa variance explained: 23.6%
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Final results:

- # - The final model is SSTsummer+SSSummer+PPspring
- # - Each of the three parameters explain an independent part of the variance in the assemblage composition, while together explaining 23.6% of the total taxa variance
- # - Sealce is excluded as it presumably explains the same part of the variance as SSTsummer
- # - SSTsummer reconstructions will reflect Sealce reconstructions (if we had decided to keep Sealce, Sealce reconstructions would reflect SSTsummer changes)
- # - PPannual and PPspring are excluded as they presumably explain the same part of the variance as PPspring does
- # - In the local calibration dataset we find three "signals" in the taxa variance regarding the 6 parameters we took into account.

References:

- # ter Braak, C.J.F., Smilauer, P., 2002. CANOCO Reference Manual and User's Guide to Canoco for Windows: Software for Canonical Community Ordination (Version 4.5), Microcomputer Power. Microcomputer Power, Ithaca, New York, U.S.A.
- # Lopes, C., Mix, A.C., Abrantes, F., 2010. Environmental controls of diatom species in northeast Pacific sediments. *Palaeogeogr. Palaeoclimatol. Palaeoecol.* 297, 188–200.
- # <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.palaeo.2010.07.029>

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